

Anterior Bilaterale Capsulophimosis Following Congenital Cataract Surgery

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Clinical Image

Anterior capsular phimosis refers to the inward fibrosis and contraction of the capsulorhexis following cataract removal. Those with zonular laxity face a higher likelihood of developing this condition. While mild to moderate instances of phimosis typically do not pose a significant visual concern, severe cases may necessitate Nd:YAG laser anterior capsulotomy for treatment.

We report a case of a 9 year-old child, who underwent cataract surgery for congenital cataract bilateral, with posterior capsulorhexis and intraocular lens implantation, In the immediate , the patient recovered, for each eye, a visual acuity of 20/40 . The patient REPORTS with 9 months of gradually progressive deterioration of vision bilateral . at the ophthalmological examination visual acuity 20/400 ,capsule contraction syndrome on 360° degrees bilateral , with a clear visual axis.the treatment is by Nd: YAG laser anterior capsulotomy.

Figure 1: photograph showing a capsulophimosis of the left eye

Figure 2: photograph showing a capsulophimosis of the right eye